

White paper on Nuclear Science in Brazil

Contribution to the Latin American Strategy Forum for Research Infrastructure

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Introduction

The atomic nucleus is a very complex quantum system with a number of constituents neither large enough to be treated entirely by statistical methods, nor low enough to be treated with analytic methods. It is a hierarchical structure composed of positively charged protons and chargeless neutrons. Protons and neutrons, generically named nucleons, are not structureless but made up of more fundamental particles, quarks and gluons. Due to the non-trivial behavior of the strong force at low energies, the latter remain confined within baryons (nucleons) and mesons (pions). From the confinement of quarks and gluons emerges a residue of the strong force, the nuclear force among nucleons primarily mediated by pions.

Recent planning documents and Long Range Plans describe the key problems of Nuclear Physics, in particular, the recent Long Range Plans of NuPECC (2017) and NSAC (2015), agree about the subjects belonging to Nuclear Science, which are:

- Hadron Physics -QCD and structure of hadrons and nuclei;
- QCD and phases of strongly interacting matter at extreme conditions
- Nuclear Structure and Reaction Dynamics
- Nuclear Astrophysics
- Fundamental Symmetries
- Applications and Societal Benefits

Many of the subjects above are in close relationship with the subjects of the field often called, “High energy physics”. The experimental activity performed mainly at the Open Laboratory of Nuclear Physics (LAFN) at IFUSP has also problems and solutions similar to the high energy physics experiments. For this reason, the nuclear physics community has an interest to join the Latin American Strategy Forum for Research Infrastructures (LASF4RI), recently launched. To pursue this intent, the situation of the field of Nuclear Science in Brazil is presented in this document.

Instituto Nacional de Ciência e Tecnologia em Física Nuclear e Aplicações (INCT-FNA), “Projeto Prof. Paulo Roberto Silveira Gomes”,

The Conselho Nacional de Ciencia e Tecnologia (CNPq), that is the federal funding agency of Brazil, has approved in 2016 the “Instituto Nacional de Ciência e Tecnologia em Física Nuclear e Aplicações (INCT-FNA), Projeto Prof. Paulo Roberto Silveira Gomes”, which is one among 101 large projects in all areas of the natural sciences. The INCT-FNA was formulated in 2014 under the leadership of Paulo Roberto Silveira Gomes.

The INCT program is one of the largest funding programs and has the following objectives:

- Development of research networks;
- Consolidation of institutional partnerships;
- Multidisciplinary approach to strategic themes for the country;
- Highly qualified human resource training and qualification;
- Long term support for research.

The INCT-FNA is based at the Universidade Federal Fluminense (UFF) in Niteroi (RJ). Due to the untimely death of Paulo Gomes in 2016, the coordination of INCT-FNA was assumed by prof. Takeshi Kodama (UFRJ-UFF) and Prof. Jesus Lubian Rios (UFF) was elected as vice-coordinator. The structure of the INCT-FNA is presented below:

The “Comitê Gestor” (Managing Committee) has five members plus the coordinator and vice-coordinator. The five members are, namely,

- Alinka Lépine-Szily (USP),
- Carlos Roberto Appoloni (UEL),
- Débora Peres Menezes (UFSC),
- Gastão Krein (UNESP)
- Luiz Carlos Chamon (USP).

The “Comitê Consultivo Internacional” (International Advisory Committee) has 27 members, 9 for each subfield and are internationally recognized experts.

The INCT-FNA has 35 institutions in 9 Brazilian states, 140 researcher members and ~60 students and post-doctoral fellows working in three large areas:

- 62 researchers in High Energy Nuclear Physics (HENP)
- 31 researchers in Nuclear Structure and Reactions (NSR)
- 47 researchers in Nuclear Physics Applications (NPA)

Figure 1. The geographical distribution of Nuclear Physics research groups in Brazil, the number is for the groups in the respective state and the letters are acronyms already defined for the fields of nuclear physics.

The groups are mainly in the South-East region (23), followed by the South (7), North-East (5), North (2) and Central-West (1). The Nuclear Physics Applications (NPA) field has many more activities in Brazil, which are not included in the INCT-FNA. The estimation is that only ~15% are included in the INCT-FNA, mainly those performed at Universities.

The direction of INCT-FNA asked the three sub-fields of the program: High-Energy Nuclear Physics, Nuclear Structure and Reactions, and Applied Nuclear Physics, to produce reports with an evaluation of the present situation and proposals for the future of each sub-field. These reports were presented at the 2nd Symposium of the INCT-FNA, realized in Niteroi at UFF, between 27 and 30 May 2019. The symposium had about 100 participants and the active participation of 9 members of the International Advisory Committee.

Achievements of INCT – FNA in 2017-2019

- 2 symposia: September 2017, May 2019
- 789 publications
- 121 IC, 91 Masters theses, 49 PhD theses, 25 Post-doctors.
- 96 scientific events organized
- International collaborations with 26 centers

For more details of INCT-FNA activities, see <https://inct-fna.if.uff.br/>

Below, we describe short profiles of the three subfields of the INCT-FNA, with a possible interest to join the Latin American Strategy Forum for Research Infrastructures (LASF4RI).

High Energy Nuclear Physics

Theory:

- Hadron theory, effective models, QCD sum rules etc. (17 researchers, at IFUSP, IFSC, UNICAMP, Mackenzie, IFT-UNESP, UCS, ITA, UFSC, UERJ, UFG, UFRGS, UFPel, UFSM)
- Compact stars, EOS with quarks and hadrons, Strong Magnetic field etc. (14 researchers at ITA, USP, UFF, UFRJ, CEFET/RJ, CBPF, UERJ, UFSC, UFRGS, FURG)
- Relativistic heavy ions, hydrodynamics, Quark Gluon Plasma etc. (10 researchers at IFUSP, UFABC, UNICAMP, EEL-USP, UNESP, UFRJ, UFF, UFSC, FURG, UFPel, UNIFAL)
- QCD phenomenology, low x and Color Glass Condensate. Diffractive pp scattering, etc. (9 researchers at IFUSP, UNICAMP, UFRJ, UFSC, UFRGS, FURG, UFPel.)
- QCD theory, Confinement and Critical Point, Lattice QCD, eq. Dyson-Schwinger etc. (6 researchers at UNICAMP, ITA, USP-SC, UCS, UERJ, UFSC, UFRJ.)

Experiment

- Ultra relativistic heavy ions, hydrodynamics, QGP etc. (3 researchers at UNICAMP)
- 2 Researchers at UFRJ of the former Auger Collaboration and Neutrino experiment (CONNIE)
- There are very few experimentalists working in Hadron Physics in Brazil
- Most LHC and RHIC experimentalists are not in INCT- FNA

Future Perspectives

- Strengthen the links between theoretical and experimental groups
- Establish stronger links among theoretical communities
- Access to high performance computing systems
- Attract new students and post-docs
- Expand and strengthen national and international collaborations
- Focus on the upcoming experiments
- Intermediate and long term planning
- Geographical expansion
- Enhancement of the collaboration with the high energy experimental groups working at LHC and RHIC within the INCT-FNA activities

- Increase the number of groups doing lattice calculations
- Increase the number of experimentalists in general and in JLAB , BESIII and future colliders
- More activity in phenomenology

Nuclear Structure and Reactions:

Theory:

- Calculations of direct reactions with breakup of radioactive and stable weakly bound nuclei (4 researchers at USP, ITA, UFRJ, UFF)
- Description of light exotic nuclei using few-body models (3 researchers at USP, ITA)
- Study of multinucleon and cluster reactions. Effect of pairing correlations (1 researcher at UFF)
- Dirac-Hartree-Fock-Bogoliubov and Dirac-Brueckner approximations for nuclear matter and finite nuclei (1 researcher at ITA.)
- Studies of stable and exotic nuclei, including pairing effects (2 researchers at USP, ITA.)
- Effective theories for weakly bound nuclear systems (3 researchers at USP, ITA)
- Study of neutrino-less double beta decay (1 researcher at UFF)

Experiments:

- Measurement of nuclear reactions with radioactive and stable beams (13 researchers at the Open Laboratory of Nuclear Physics (LAFN) at IFUSP.)
- Measurement of nuclear reactions with astrophysical interest (2-3 researchers at LAFN)
- Measurement of resonant scattering of light particles (p, d, alpha) with radioactive or stable projectiles in inverse kinematics. (3 researchers at LAFN.)
- Measurement of isomeric states and half-lives using γ spectroscopy. (1-3 researchers at LAFN)
- Measurement of coherent neutrino scattering by nuclei (CONNIE) (1 researcher at UFRJ)

Experimental Facilities in Brazil for Nuclear Structure and Reactions

Concerning the experimental activities, they are performed at the Open Laboratory for Nuclear Physics (LAFN) at the Institute of Physics of the University of Sao Paulo (IFUSP). LAFN is equipped with a Tandem Accelerator, Pelletron 8UD, which produces stable beams of energies around 5 MeVA maximum. There are two particle accelerators dedicated to basic nuclear physics in South America, the one at LAFN and another Pelletron tandem, called Tandar, at Commission Nacional de Energia Atomica (CNEA) in Buenos Aires, Argentina.

Figure 2. The 8UD Pelletron Tandem Accelerator of the Open Laboratory of Nuclear Physics (LAFN) of the Institute of Physics of USP

The experimental hall of LAFN has several beamlines with different equipment: large multipurpose scattering chamber, special beam line for applications, Enge Split-Pole magnetic spectrometer, HPGe array with mini-ball for particle detection.

In 2004, the RIBRAS system, acronym standing for “Radioactive Ion Beams in Brasil”, became operational at LAFN, connected to the 8 MV Pelletron accelerator. It delivers light radioactive ion beams, such as ${}^6\text{He}$, ${}^8\text{Li}$, ${}^7\text{Be}$, ${}^{10}\text{Be}$, ${}^{12}\text{B}$, and ${}^8\text{B}$, produced by transfer reactions, which are separated, and focused by two superconducting solenoids. It is the first such equipment in the Southern Hemisphere and the only one in Latin America.

Figure 3. Photograph of the RIBRAS system installed on the 45B beam line of the Experimental hall of the LAFN. The stable beam comes from the left and the production target is located before the first solenoid. Experiments can be performed in the central chamber between the 2 solenoids or in the large scattering chamber after the second solenoid on the right side of the picture.

Transfer reactions can produce Radioactive Ion Beams (RIB) at much lower energies and, in this way, small laboratories with quite low energy accelerators, are making important contributions. At energies around the Coulomb barrier, valuable information can be obtained on the structure of exotic nuclei and on the dynamics of the nuclear reactions among them. Important issues, such as fusion below the Coulomb barrier, and the role of the neutron halo with respect to fusion, can be studied only with low energy beams.

LAFN has about 60-70 users including staff members, post-docs, graduate students and external users. It has a Project Advisory Committee (PAC). The main interest is in nuclear reactions with weakly bound projectiles, stable or radioactive.

Visibility

The research groups are known in the international Nuclear Structure and Reactions community, due to publications and participation at international conferences. For the theoretical groups the visibility is well attested by the number of invited talks and international collaborations. For the experimentalists at LAFN the effort to remain competitive is continuous, and the recent approval of a thematic project of FAPESP will allow a large upgrade of detection and acquisition systems. They publish in prestigious journals, present their results at international conferences and have several international collaborations.

International Collaboration

It is a very important part of the research activity, and is well established for the theoretical groups. LAFN collaborates mainly with similar low or medium energy laboratories. For the future, formal collaboration should be established with new large research installations, which are in construction now, and where the field of Nuclear Structure and Reactions have important future research plans. The interest of the funding agencies is clearly the internationalization of the Brazilian science.

Future perspectives

- Expansion to other regions and states in Brazil
- Plans for new experimental infrastructure for NSR in future. Accelerator for radioisotope production + basic research in NSR with higher energy radioactive and also stable ion beams.

Nuclear Physics Applications

The Nuclear Physics Applications cover scientific studies in a wide range of areas using well established knowledge and developing new procedures, equipment and solutions to answer basic science queries in other disciplines, benefiting the society with state-of-the-art technology

and contributing to a healthy cooperation between universities and the public and private productive sector

Figure 4. Radiocarbon Laboratory (LAC) of UFF

The Fluminense Federal University stands out for having the only facility for Accelerator Mass Spectrometry in South America with a complete sample preparation and measurement facility, a world recognized laboratory and center of reference for the Latin American community, responsible for hosting the First Latin American Radiocarbon Conference in 2019.

The LAMFI (Laboratory for Material analyses using ion beams) has an 1.7MV Pelletron accelerator for ion beam analyses comprising several fields, such as effects of radiation on electronic circuits, environmental studies and archaeometry.

Figure 5. Photograph of a beam line of LAMFI

Experimental Facilities

- USP: LAMFI: Tandem-Pelletron accelerator 1.7 MV for ion beam analyses
- UFF: LAC-UFF: ^{14}C Accelerator Mass Spectrometry (sample preparation and dedicated 250 kV accelerator mass spectrometer); LARAMAM: gamma spectroscopy
- UFBA: Stable Isotope Studies, new ^{14}C sample preparation laboratory in construction
- UEL: X-ray and gamma spectroscopy, new ^{14}C sample preparation laboratory in construction

- FEI: gamma ray applications for environmental monitoring, X-ray diffractometry, high performance electrical characterization
- UNESP: IBB Mass spectrometry
- UESC: Atomic force microscope (being installed)
- UFABC: simulations for biomedical applications

International collaborations

The Applied Physics research groups are involved in several international collaborations as:

- the ATTO project with the Max Planck Institute from Germany,
- an observatory in the Amazon Forest for environmental studies,
- the study of past fires within the whole Amazon basin, with Exeter University, UK
- the PIRE-CREATE project with the NSF from USA, for studying climate changes based of growth rings from trees and speleothem.

Future Perspectives

- Expand the use of ^{14}C Accelerator Mass Spectrometry in Brazil
- Foster collaborations between the private and public productive sectors
- Promote the establishment of startup companies based on the research developed within the INCT-FNA
- Increase the number of institutions with ^{14}C preparation laboratories for optimizing the use of the SSAMS at LAC-UFF
- Diffusion of science to general public emphasizing the benefits of Applied Physics
- Promote scientific collaborations among different research groups within INCT-FNA and with other INCTs
- Bring together the Latin American Radiocarbon community
- Expand the use of Nuclear Applications in Archaeometry
- Promote collaborations between accelerator based medical physics and general ion beam analysis